

ELECTROSPINNING OF POLYMER NANOCOMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

This study investigates problems in the electrospinning of polymer nanocomposites, such as beading and fibre break up. A comprehensive process model has been developed and computer simulations have been performed to analyse the electrospinning of polymer nanocomposites as compared to the electrospinning of the corresponding polymers. The study focuses on differences in the viscoelastic properties and surface tension.

Keywords: Electrospinning, nanocomposites, modelling, viscoelasticity, surface tension

1. ISSUES IN THE ELECTROSPINNING OF POLYMER NANOCOMPOSITES

Electrospinning of polymers and polymer nanocomposites is of great interest in a number of fields, such as biomedical scaffolds for tissue engineering, electrofunctional textiles, fibrous mats or porous films to be used as electrodes or other electrical and electronic applications. It offers the possibility of producing nanofibres of controlled fibre diameter, laid as a random mat or as an oriented structure with controlled fibre orientation. Fig.1 presents examples of a gelatine scaffold and a hydroxyapatite-gelatine nanocomposite fibre scaffold, both fabricated by A.A.Salifu, a mat of MWCNT-PVA (multi-wall carbon nanotube-poly(vinyl alcohol)) nanocomposite fibres and a deposition of discontinuous MWCNT-polyurethane fibrils, both fabricated by Y.C.Chau. In general, the nanocomposite continuous fibres contain “beads” for both the hydroxyapatite nanoparticles in gelatine and the MWCNT-PVA system. Although one would tend to think that the beads might be due to agglomerates of nanoparticles, beading also occurs in the electrospinning of polymer fibres and is due to the balance and effects of forces during the electrospinning process. Zhou et al [1] attributed the presence of surface irregularities and beading in the electrospinning of MWCNT-PEO and MWCNT-PVA nanofibres to the elastic deformation and coiling of MWCNTs, which could be clearly seen inside the fibres when examined by HRTEM. Similarly, fibre break up, which results in a spray of droplets or discontinuous fibres may occur in the electrospinning of polymers but it is more frequent in the electrospinning of nanocomposites.

As a result, a model of the electrospinning process has been developed and validated, and computer simulations were performed in parametric studies where the focus was on polymeric nanocomposite materials and the differences of their processing by electrospinning from the processing of the corresponding polymers.

Fig.1. Electrospun mats of (a) gelatine fibres (b) hydroxyapatite-gelatine nanocomposite fibres (c) MWCNT-PVA nanocomposite fibres (d) MWCNT-polyurethane nanocomposite.

2. PROCESS MODELLING

The process model developed for this study is a combination of models for electrospinning [2] and drop formation [3] containing inertia terms, viscoelastic terms, the electric field terms, surface tension and gravity. The final process model consists of two one-dimensional equations originating from the kinematic boundary condition, the normal and tangential components of the traction boundary condition and the z-component of the momentum equation:

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} \right) = -\gamma \frac{\partial(2H)}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial z} + \frac{(I - \kappa \pi R^2 E)E}{\pi R^2 u} + g\rho \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial R}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial R}{\partial z} = -\frac{1}{2} R \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} \quad (2)$$

where R is the radius of the jet (or drop) at an axial position z and time t, u is the axial velocity, g is the gravity, γ is the surface tension, E is the electric field, I is the current, κ is the electrical conductivity of the suspension, σ is the viscoelastic stress and 2H is given by

$$2H = \frac{1}{R[1 + (\partial R / \partial z)^2]^{1/2}} - \frac{\partial^2 R / \partial z^2}{[1 + (\partial R / \partial z)^2]^{3/2}} \quad (3)$$

Table 1. Dimensionless groups important in jet flow, jet break-up and electrospinning

$\text{Reynolds Number (Re)} = \frac{\rho U_o 2R_n}{\mu} = \frac{\text{InertiaForces}}{\text{ViscousForces}}$
$\text{Capillary Number (Ca)} = \frac{\mu U_o}{\gamma} = \frac{\text{ViscousForces}}{\text{SurfaceTension}}$
$\text{Weber No (We)} = \frac{\rho U_o^2 (2R_n)}{\gamma} = \frac{\text{InertiaForces}}{\text{SurfaceTension}}$
<p>Also Rayleigh time scale for capillary break up (t_r) =</p> $\sqrt{\frac{\rho(2R_n)}{\gamma}}$
$\text{Euler Number (Eu)} = \frac{\epsilon_o E^2}{\rho U_o^2} = \frac{\text{ElectrostaticForces}}{\text{InertiaForces}}$
$\text{Ohnesorge Number (Oh)} = \frac{\mu}{(\rho \gamma R_o)^{1/2}}$
$\text{Deborah Number (De)} = \frac{\text{RelaxationTime}}{\text{ProcessTime}}$

Table 1 presents the important dimensionless groups that govern the process.

3. MATERIALS AND PROPERTIES

The electrospun polymer solutions consisted of 12 w.t.% polyurethane in DMF (N,N-dimethyl formamide); two different polyurethane grades were used, PU3685 and PU3690, respectively, supplied by Bayer. The electrospun nanocomposite suspensions were based on the above solutions with the addition of multiwall carbon nanotubes at 5% b.w. of polyurethane, resulting in the corresponding systems of PU3685+CNTs and PU3690+CNTs.

Surface tension was determined via the pendant drop method using a Kruss EasyDrop. The PU3685 solution had a surface tension of 38.1 mN/m and the PU3690 solution had a surface tension of 41 mN/m.

Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) was carried out using an RDA II Rheometrics in the parallel plate configuration to determine the elastic modulus and the viscosity of the solutions. The results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Data obtained by DMA for each solution used in electrospinning

	PU3685	PU3690	PU3685+CNTs	PU3690+CNTs
Elastic shear modulus (Pa)	454	470	490	5789
Shear Viscosity (Pas):				
Consistency (SI units)	7.12	30.31	47.24	22.28
Power law index	0.12	0.38	0.10	0.22
Elastic tensile modulus (Pa)	19.5	23	21	248
Elongational Viscosity (Pas):				
Consistency (SI units)	1	2.3	1.7	1.5
Power law index	0.12	0.38	0.10	0.22

Fig.2 presents the viscosity data and their best line fit for each material system.

Fig.2. DMA in shear mode: Viscosity data and their best line fit.

4. ELECTROSPINNING:

EXPERIMENTAL RUNS AND COMPUTER SIMULATIONS

Experimental runs were carried out at an electric potential of 25 kV. The solution was supplied by a syringe pump at a constant flowrate of 4 ml/hr. It emerged in downwards flow from a needle of 0.84 mm internal diameter. Under the influence of an electric field of 25 kV/150 mm, it flowed downwards onto a rotating wire drum of 120 mm diameter and 300 mm length, rotating at a speed of 2 rpm.

The process satisfied the Rayleigh condition: $E(\pi R_o \gamma)^{-1/2} < 4$, hence a Taylor cone was formed in all case-studies. After the cone formation, the flow continued either in the

form of fibres or fibre break up occurred with possible drop formation. Given that the outlet needle electrode was of 0.84 mm diameter and the deposition substrate had a length of 300 mm, the flow was in the form of multiple continuous fibres or a spray, opening as a fan in the downwards flow. Given the high solvent concentration (about 88%) and its high boiling point (153 °C), the fibre or drop diameter and radius, R , in flight is assumed to correspond to the dimensions of the wet jet, whereas the radius, R_{dry} , of the fibres or drops of the dry mat deposited on the substrate is smaller, as described by the relation

$$R = R_{wet} = R_{dry} (1/w_s)^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

where w_s is the solid fraction representing the polyurethane and CNTs.

Case-study: PU3685

Fig.3. PU3685: Optical micrograph of the dry deposited product and simulation predictions.

Fig.3 presents an optical micrograph of the dry deposited product where it is clear that the process did not result in fibre mat formation but in a product with coalesced islands of polyurethane film material. There is also evidence of splashing in the circled regions. The computer simulations predicted fibre break up and formation of a relatively large drop. The simulation time was very short. If the simulation was continued, it is expected that the liquid polyurethane solution droplet would grow and it might be a relatively large drop when reaching the substrate, splashing, spreading and coalescing with other neighbouring liquid drops, finally flattening to a discontinuous film after solvent evaporation. The break up phenomenon can be attributed to the low relaxation time and low Deborah number of the PU3685 solution ($De = 0.19$) compared to the corresponding values in the case-studies where fibres were formed.

Case-study: PU3690

Fig.4. PU3690:
SEM micrographs of the dry deposited product and simulation predictions.

Fig.4 presents the experimental results and simulation predictions for the electrospinning of PU3690. It is clear that this polymer solution resulted in fibre formation, which was also predicted by the computer model. The low magnification SEM micrograph presents an area of about $10^4 \mu\text{m}^2$ in which there is evidence of beading in the fibres. No beading was predicted by the computer model for PU3690 possibly due to the relatively large $\Delta z = 4 \mu\text{m}$ selected for the numerical simulation to save computer memory and time. The large Δz did not allow the computer model to resolve meso-scale disturbances such as beading or micro-scale disturbances such as the small waviness of the fibre surface that can be observed in the high magnification SEM micrograph. After solvent evaporation, the predicted wet fibre diameter $2R = 0.92 \mu\text{m}$ corresponds to a predicted dry fibre diameter of $0.32 \mu\text{m}$ (according to equation (4)), which is in excellent agreement with the diameter of the dry fibres in the SEM micrograph in Fig.4. A higher Deborah number, $De = 0.45$, was calculated for the PU3690 solution, which stabilises the jet leading to fibre formation, although it is still low and, hence, there is some beading in the fibres.

Case-study: PU3685 + CNTs

Fig.5. PU3685 + CNTs: SEM micrographs of the dry deposited product and simulation predictions.

Fig.5 presents the experimental results and simulation predictions for the electrospinning of PU3685 + CNTs. It is clear that this suspension resulted in fibre formation, which was also predicted by the computer model. The low magnification SEM micrograph presents an area of about $10^4 \mu\text{m}^2$ in which there is evidence of thin fibres with very little beading in the fibres. No beading was predicted by the computer model for PU3690 possibly due to the relatively large $\Delta z = 6 \mu\text{m}$ selected for the numerical simulation to save computer memory and time. The large Δz did not allow the computer model to resolve meso-scale disturbances such as beading or nano-scale disturbances such as the small waviness of the fibre surface that can be observed in the high magnification SEM micrograph. After solvent evaporation, the predicted wet fibre diameter $2R = 0.52 \mu\text{m}$ corresponds to a predicted dry fibre diameter of $0.18 \mu\text{m}$ (according to equation (4)), which is in excellent agreement with the diameter of the dry fibres in the SEM micrograph in Fig.5. The PU3685 + CNTs suspension has the highest Deborah number, $De = 1.3$, which stabilises the jet leading to fibre formation with minimum beading, despite the presence of CNTs.

Case-study: PU3690 + CNTs

Fig.6. PU3690 + CNTs:
Optical micrograph of the dry deposited product and simulation predictions.

Fig.6 presents an optical micrograph of the dry deposited product of the PU3690 + CNTs system where it is clear that the process did not result in fibre mat formation but in a product with large deposited drops of 10-15 μm size, inter-dispersed within a spray of smaller droplets. The computer simulations predicted fibre break up and formation of a large drop which after drying matches the size of the large deposited drops in the optical micrograph. The spray of the smaller drops in the micrograph seems to be the satellite droplets generated in the break up which probably resulted in one large drop and several smaller satellite droplets. This was not fully captured by the computer simulation as the simulation time was very short. The break up phenomena can be attributed to the low relaxation time and low Deborah number of the PU3690 + CNTs suspension as it had the lowest relaxation time and lowest Deborah number ($De = 0.0016$ to 0.04 , depending on the estimated fibre diameter) of all case-studies.

5. CONCLUSIONS

A computer program was constructed to describe the flow and shape evolution in electrospinning. It was based on a physical model which included inertia terms, viscoelastic terms, the electric field terms, surface tension and gravity; the equations were solved using an explicit finite volume/finite difference method. In order to avoid lengthy computer runs and too high memory requirements, the program was run for very short total process time, which proved sufficient for the monitoring of the fastest growing instability (at a frequency ω_{\max}) and for detecting the major break up events but it missed lower frequency instabilities. A constant time step $\Delta t = 0.01 \mu s$ was set and it was the same for all case-studies. To maintain numerical stability in the explicit solver for this value of Δt , a relatively large finite length Δz was set of the order of $1 \mu m$, with

variations in each case-study as Δz would determine the finite process time $\Delta t_{\text{process}}$, which was set in each case-study proportionally to the relaxation time of the solution or suspension of that case-study. In this case, the computer model included the effect of the Deborah number on the fastest growing instability.

The computer model was validated using four case-studies which included two polymer solutions, each with a different polyurethane grade of different rheological characteristics, and two MWCNT-polymer suspensions which included the corresponding polyurethane grade and MWCNTs at the same composition. In terms of physical properties, there was a small difference in the value of surface tension between the solutions in the range of 38-41 mN/m, which at this level was thought that it did not make any difference in the process and product. The viscoelastic properties were the most important factors for the differences in the process and product of the four case-studies, and most significantly the relaxation time and Deborah number. Small Deborah numbers resulted in break up as it was captured in the simulations and did not lead to any fibre mats in the experiments. Larger Deborah numbers resulted in jet stabilisation, predicted fibre formation, and stable fibres with minimum beading in the experiments. The presence of MWCNTs did not necessarily lead to worse results in electrospinning, as there was no fibre formation in the low viscosity polymer solution PU3685 and the very low Deborah number suspension PU3690+CNTs. On the other hand, the higher Deborah number suspension PU3685+CNTs resulted in the formation of thin fibres with minimum beading, despite the presence of CNTs. The polymer solution PU3690 with intermediate Deborah number resulted in the formation of thicker fibres with more beading than the PU3685+CNTs system. This study does not include any HRTEM of the PU3685+CNTs fibres to investigate any possible correlations between the shape of MWCNTs in the fibre and the measured viscoelastic properties.

The computer simulations successfully predicted the major break up events and the fibre diameter. They did not capture the beading and the small waviness on the fibre surface possibly due to the relatively large finite length Δz , large time step Δt and short total simulation time used in this study.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to gratefully acknowledge IeMRC/EPSRC for funding P.Wilson.

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